

Unleashing Curiosity: Teachers' Experiences and Strategies for Cultivating Critical Thinking Skills Through Inquiry-Based Learning

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Abstract. Inquiry-based learning continues to be recognized for its potential to cultivate critical thinking and promote student-centered engagement in secondary education. This qualitative study, grounded in phenomenological research design, investigated the lived experiences of secondary school teachers in implementing inquiry-based learning and its perceived influence on students' critical thinking development. Using in-depth interviews as the primary data collection method, the study engaged participants whose insights were analyzed through thematic analysis to identify significant patterns and meanings. The research was guided by three central questions: the first examined teachers' lived experiences with inquiry-based learning; the second identified strategies employed to enhance students' critical thinking; and the third explored the values and educational implications derived from these experiences. Findings revealed key themes related to the shifting teacher roles, increased student engagement, and pedagogical adaptability. In terms of instructional strategies, participants emphasized scaffolding support, intentional inquiry design, and collaborative learning as essential in fostering critical thinking. Additionally, the study highlighted values centered on student autonomy and an emphasis on the learning process. These findings contribute to the broader discourse on inquiry-based pedagogy and underscore its relevance in shaping reflective, cognitively enriched classroom practices.

KEY WORDS

1. critical thinking 2. inquiry-based learning 3. secondary teachers

Date Received: April 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: May 15, 2025 — Date Published: June 18, 2025

1. Introduction

Inquisitiveness is an admirable and powerful trait that drives human progress and understanding. However, while many people may be filled with questions, not everyone takes the necessary steps to seek out answers. True curiosity goes beyond merely wondering. It requires action, exploration, and a willingness to delve deeper into the unknown. It is through this active pursuit of knowledge that we discover new insights and learn more about the world around us. In the field of education, curiosity is particularly significant, as it serves as the foundation for critical thinking, a vital skill that students must cultivate. Our societal needs have tremendously changed over the years. Teachers need to think of their students and the challenges that are ahead of them. In Bangladesh, Saavedra and Opfer (2020) emphasizes the critical

role of inquiry-based learning in fostering 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving. The analyzed education systems across multiple countries, found that inquiry-based learning enhances students' engagement and deepens their understanding by promoting active participation in learning processes. This approach not only improves academic outcomes but also prepares students for the complexities of modern life and work, making inquiry-based learning a vital educational strategy globally. In Pakistan, et al., (2022) examined the elements, importance, and implementation of inquiry-based learning within the teaching and learning process. Their findings emphasize the vital role of teachers in adopting this approach to help learners develop essential 21st-century skills such as creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication. However, the study also reveals that traditional teaching methods remain widely used, which limits student engagement and restricts the development of higher-order thinking skills. These conventional approaches often discourage learners from exploring ideas independently, asking questions, and constructing their understanding. While the benefits of inquiry-based learning are evident, its consistent application in classrooms remains a challenge, especially in settings where conventional instruction still prevails. In the same page, Gu et al. (2015, as cited from Gholam, 2019) an article in China and has found that students involved in inquiry-based practices have reported higher levels of academic self-efficacy, resolved conflicts at a higher rate, been less afraid to take risks, and more likely to continue trying different ways to be successful when they failed. Students who are actively engaged in inquiry do not only master content but master habits of mind. They further added that developing understanding through students' own thinking and reasoning has many benefits for students including: enjoyment and satisfaction in finding out for them-

elves something that they want to know, seeing for themselves what works rather than just being told. The problem with the critical thinking of students persists in the Philippines. Marquez (2019) found that a considerable number of students exhibited difficulty in analyzing and synthesizing information, as well as in making reasoned judgments. The article attributes this to the predominantly rote learning and teacher-centered instructional methods commonly used in many public and private schools. These traditional approaches often limit opportunities for students to engage in inquiry-based activities or problem-solving tasks that would foster critical thinking development. Based on the journal of Perez (2018) in Bulacan. He pointed out that while the Philippine K-12 curriculum includes critical thinking as a key competency, its integration into daily classroom practices remains inconsistent. Many teachers struggle with implementing strategies that actively promote critical thinking due to large class sizes, limited resources, and insufficient training. As a result, students tend to focus on memorization of facts rather than engaging in reflective and analytical thinking. Addressing these gaps requires professional development for teachers to enhance their instructional practices and incorporate more learner-centered, inquiry-driven approaches. In the same thread of thought, multiple-choice questions and factual recall, do not adequately measure students' ability to think critically. A published work by Lopez (2022) in La Union, recommends the use of performance-based assessments and projects that require students to apply reasoning, analyze complex issues, and construct evidence-based arguments. This shift in assessment strategies is seen as essential in cultivating a culture of critical thinking in Philippine classrooms. In the local scene, Bogador et al. (2024) highlights both the benefits and challenges faced by teachers and students in inquiry-based learning. They found that it significantly improved students' engage-

ment and critical thinking skills, particularly in science and social studies subjects, where students were encouraged to ask questions, explore concepts, and conduct investigations. However, this also revealed obstacles, such as limited access to resources, large class sizes, and the need for teacher training in inquiry-based pedagogies. In summation, inquiry-based learning has been considered in different context in different classroom environment. The challenges pertaining to employment has been put into light. A significant research gap in the study of inquiry-based learning and critical thinking lies in the inconsistent implementation and measurement of these approaches across diverse educational contexts. While numerous studies confirm the benefits of inquiry-based learning in promoting critical thinking, there is limited research on the specific factors that influence its effectiveness, such as teacher training, classroom environment, and cultural differences in teaching styles (Wale Bishaw, 2020). Despite the recognized potential of inquiry-based learning in promoting critical thinking, its implementation remains inconsistent and is often not well understood across different educational settings. A significant concern is the lack of research on important factors, such as teacher preparation, classroom environment, and cultural influences on teaching practices, which may affect their success (Wale Bishaw, 2020). This inconsistency limits the development of critical thinking skills among learners and restricts the broader application of inquiry-based approaches. As the demand for learners to develop higher-order thinking skills continues to grow in a complex and rapidly changing world, there is a clear need to investigate these gaps. Therefore, it is timely and necessary to explore the conditions that contribute to or hinder the effective use of inquiry-based learning in enhancing critical thinking. In the local context published in Davao del Sur, there is a noticeable lack of revisions examining how the inquiry-based approach supports the development of students' critical thinking. In particular, some schools have observed that students struggle to engage meaningfully in classroom activities. Many learners exhibit minimal interest in exploring topics in depth, which limits their ability to question, analyze, and draw logical conclusions. Additionally, classroom participation is often affected by low motivation and frequent distractions, including the use of mobile phones during lessons. These issues limit students' opportunities to develop essential thinking skills through active inquiry. The lack of localized research on these challenges underscores the need to investigate how inquiry-based learning can be effectively applied to foster critical thinking among students. This study aims to address this gap by examining the role of inquiry-based instruction in promoting critical thinking within the educational setting of Davao del Sur.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study investigated and analyzed the experiences and strategies utilized high school teachers to foster students' critical thinking through inquiry-based approach. The study provided useful insights into the inquiry-based approach used by teachers to hone students' critical thinking. In the end, the study increased my understanding about the pedagogical practices, especially the inquiry-based approach in unleashing students' critical thinking. This have helped me reflect on what I can do as educator to offer guidance and assistance to them. The central objective of this data collection revolved around capturing the real-life experiences of teacher in their inquiry-based approach in teaching. The outcomes of this phenomenological learning provided me with a deeper understanding of the how teaching is a transformative profession and how teachers can help in honing important facets a skills necessary for the growth of these students. Furthermore, I assessed the efficacy of these strategies

1.3. Significant of the Study—Putting into consideration the cited problem situation, I found it timely to conduct this study. This brought the necessity to conduct an inquiry about the experiences and strategies of teachers in cultivating students' critical thinking skills as well as values that are deemed necessary and useful. I hope that this study enlightens the identified sectors of the academe. This includes the teachers and learners.

Teachers

The teachers may gain practical insights into the use of inquiry-based learning in the classroom. The findings may guide them in enhancing their instructional strategies and fostering a more active and reflective learning environment. This may also encourage professional growth as teachers reflect on and refine their teaching approaches to support student learning better.

Learners

The study may benefit learners as it explores teaching strategies that support the development of critical thinking skills. By highlighting the role of inquiry-based learning, the study may contribute to more engaging and meaningful learning experiences that encourage students to think deeply and independently.

Inquiry-Based Learning This is characterized as a collection of classroom practices that enhance student learning via guided and progressively independent exploration of intricate questions and challenges. This is characterized as a collection of classroom practices that enhance student learning via guided and progressively independent exploration of intricate questions and challenges. It highlights the importance of student curiosity, critical thinking, and the active creation of knowledge. In this methodology, the teacher functions not merely

as a provider of information, but as a facilitator who assists learners in the process of formulating significant questions, collecting and evaluating information, and reaching conclusions based on evidence. Inquiry-Based Learning empowers students to take charge of their educational journey, frequently through teamwork, practical problem-solving, and introspective thought processes. By participating in inquiry, learners cultivate advanced cognitive abilities such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of information. This approach is particularly effective in developing critical thinking skills, as it compels students to substantiate their reasoning, explore various viewpoints, and utilize their knowledge in innovative situations. In the scope of this research, Inquiry-Based Learning is analyzed not merely as a teaching method but also as a transformative approach that allows educators to tap into students' natural curiosity and promote a more profound engagement with the material through genuine inquiry experiences.

Critical Thinking This is described as a methodical and deliberate process of using the intellect to actively and competently think through, apply, analyze, synthesize, or assess information. It requires methodical, evidence-based, logical, open-minded, and disciplined thinking. Beyond just learning facts, critical thinking calls on students to analyze presumptions, identify hidden values, draw logical conclusions, and take into account opposing views. Critical thinking is not just a result but also a skill that can be developed in educational settings using active learning techniques like inquiry-based learning. Teachers give students the chance to practice critical thinking in relevant and meaningful ways by posing real-world problems and motivating them to research, reason, and reflect.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on the

Discovery Learning Theory proposed by Jerome Bruner (1961, as cited in Yilmaz Bilican, 2020).

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

It is a method of Inquiry-Based Instruction. The theory proposes that learners construct their own knowledge and do this by organizing and categorizing information using a coding system. Bruner believed that the most effective way to develop a coding system is to discover it rather than being told by the teacher. Learning takes place in problem solving situations where the learner draws on his or her own past experience and existing knowledge to discover facts and relationships and new truths to be learned. As applied in the context of this study, a Theory of Discovery Learning argues that students learn best when they discover information for themselves. Meanwhile, inquiry-based learning promotes discovery by allowing students to pose questions, investigate, and explore topics with guidance from the teacher. This active process encourages deeper understanding and retention of knowledge. Hence, the theory proposed by Jerome Bruner would help the researcher in analyzing how inquiry-based approach holds a significant role as a pedagogical

practice and how it is honing the teaching-learning process. Moreover, the study was further reinforced by the Critical Thinking Framework by Paul and Elder (1997, cited in Shamboul, 2022). This framework emphasizes eight elements of reasoning (purpose, question, information, interpretation, concept, assumptions, implications, and point of view) and intellectual standards (clarity, accuracy, precision, relevance, depth, breadth, logic, and fairness). It is widely used in education and other fields to encourage deeper understanding, improved decision-making, and effective problem-solving. To simplify, the Critical Thinking Framework is comprehensive model that helps individuals develop and enhance their critical thinking skills through structured reasoning, analysis, and evaluation. Teachers guide learners in applying intellectual standards to evaluate the quality of their thinking and evidence. Thus, this theory is used by the researcher in order to illuminate how inquiry-based learning unleash the curiosity and critical thinking in secondary school set-up.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addressed the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explained the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offered thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concluded by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Žukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study.

Ontology

This section of the study focused on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. The authors also asserted that the research participants' perceptions of reality were varied and subjective. This study recognized the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by secondary school teachers in terms of an inquiry-based approach to learning. Every teacher's story added to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. It was my sole responsibility to employ theme analysis to capture

these various realities and provide a comprehensive picture of the experiences, strategies, and values that teachers employed in their inquiry-based approach to developing students' critical thinking.

Epistemology

Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), the researcher made an effort to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced collection of data. This approach supports the gathering of firsthand experiences and strategies, which are critical in exploring the subjective realities of the participants.

Axiology

It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study is crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I handled each participant's narrative with care and integrity, and I have the utmost respect for the information they provide. This commitment guarantees that the experiences of the teachers are communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values. Methodology According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice

and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes.” Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This study explores the experiences of secondary school teachers in relation to their employment of inquiry-based learning to develop students’ critical thinking skills. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, certain techniques like focus groups and interviews are employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants’ stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants’ ex-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal was to explore the experiences of secondary school teachers in relation to their employment of inquiry-based learning to develop students’ critical thinking skills from Davao del Norte. My objective was to gather information about their experiences, strategies, and values in relation to the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study’s qualitative researcher, I supported a level of investigation that goes beyond cur-

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Determining the precise approach used in a study is crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study’s objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammerley (2013, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) states that studies characterized by verbal rather than statistical analysis are appropriate for qual-

periences. Rhetoric In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions in order to sway the audience’s opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the voices of the participants while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only makes the research easier to read but also guarantees that the interpretations are strong and based on the experiences of the participants.

sory observations. My research aims to investigate the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasize the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives that are shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of inquiry-based learning, my study places a strong emphasis on in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants’ narratives. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the experiences, challenges, strategies, and values related to inquiry-based learning all while upholding phenomenological principles.

itative research. Since I studied the lived experiences, strategies, and values of secondary school teachers in relation to their employment of inquiry-based learning to develop students’ critical thinking skills. The qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that rather than establishing or refuting theories, I described and elaborated on this phenomenon. There are, however, specialized methods used in

qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the lived experiences of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a

phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, my goal was to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' experience about inquiry-based learning. I collected information from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (2018) recommends 5 to twenty-five. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research.

Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002 as cited in Mullet, 2018). The participants of the study were ten (10) secondary school teachers from Carmen National High School within the division of Davao del Norte. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: must be a secondary school teacher from the said school, must be teaching for more than three (3) years, applies inquiry-based learning as a pedagogical practice in class, and willing to participate in the study. I utilized the universal sampling design so that the participants are chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996 as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were crucial because they related to the moral principles and guidelines that governed my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensured that I carried out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect

and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhered to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020).

2.6. Role of the Researcher—

As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I was responsible for ensuring that the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encouraged the open and honest exploration of ideas and promoted fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helped to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensured that the findings were reliable and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I was familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possessed the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and that the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allowed me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered information from various sources such as interviews or observations, and I ensured accurate and secure storage of this information. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination and understand-

ing. This careful management of data helped maintain the integrity of the research process and supported the production of credible, reliable findings that could be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allowed me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contributed significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entailed skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured that the research results were easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helped to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they were not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps were taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed.

Securing Endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal To initiate the

data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the last two weeks of October 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before proceeding with the collection of

data. This proactive approach not only facilitates compliance with ethical standards but also fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Their support not only validated the research within the educational communities but also fostered the active collaboration of participants, which greatly aided in the efficient and prompt execution of the data collection stage. Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was undertaken during the first two weeks of November 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals are in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for Permission from the School Heads Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collec-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulate conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and

tion timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the third week of November 2024 to the last week of the same month.

Obtaining Consent from the Participants With the school heads' approval, I asked consent from the research participants, who are teachers, through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensures that participant is fully informed and agree to participate. Asking for consent from both participants was done in the last week of November 2024.

Conducting the Interview Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of Decemeber 2024.

Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure used audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was done for the third week of December 2024.

perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which is particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within

qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis is both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I start categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes are examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entails combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information. The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I made use of Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences in inquiry-based learning. Accord-

ing to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which is validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018).

Data Familiarization By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aimed to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process was crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. **Identifying Significant Statements** I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that was directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data, such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews, had to be conducted. This step was essential to ensuring that my analysis stayed on topic and provided a strong basis for future thematic development. **Formulating Meanings** After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings that were pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admitted that complete bracketing was never truly possible, I had to reflexively "bracket" my own presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stayed

rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entailed putting aside my own interpretations as much as was practical. Clustering Themes I ensured a rigorous analysis that remained true to the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes that were shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions had to be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserved the integrity of the analysis. Developing an Exhaustive Description I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description sought to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it was ensured that the final representation presented a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant had had. Producing the Fundamental Structure I broke

down the lengthy explanation into a succinct, concise statement that highlighted the key elements that I believed were crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. The essence of the participants' experiences was effectively and concisely communicated through this succinct synthesis, which concentrated on the essential components that were necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking Verification of the Fundamental Structure I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflected their experience, either by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might have gone back and changed the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased and the analysis was kept firmly based on the perspectives of the participants. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The trustworthiness of a study is about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba and Lincoln (1981, as cited in Creswell, 2018).

Credibility

Credibility involves ensuring that the findings genuinely reflect the realities of those who shared their experiences. In research focusing on teaching practices such as the inquiry-based

approach, credibility is critical as it determines whether the voices of educators are accurately represented. To strengthen this aspect, the researcher engaged with participants over an extended period, allowing a deeper understanding of how they apply inquiry-based learning in their classrooms. Data were gathered from multiple sources, including interviews, classroom observations, and reflective accounts, to provide a more comprehensive picture of their experiences. Participants were also invited to review and confirm the interpretations through member checking, which helped ensure that the findings accurately captured their insights and perspectives.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study (Ritchie and Spencer 2019)

Transferability

Transferability pertains to the extent to which the findings of this study can be applied to other educational settings or groups. While the data are rooted in the specific experiences of secondary school teachers using inquiry-based instruction, I provided detailed, thick descriptions of the research context, participants, and procedures. These detailed accounts allow other educators, particularly those in similar educational systems or pedagogical environments, to assess the relevance and applicability of the findings to their settings. In this way, the study supports informed decision-making for curriculum planners, teacher trainers, and fellow researchers interested in implementing inquiry-based practices.

Confirmability

Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. In my study, I ensured that the findings are derived from the participants' narratives rather than from personal biases or assumptions. To uphold this standard, I maintained a detailed audit trail documenting every phase of the research process, including data collection methods, coding procedures, and analytical decisions. I also practiced reflexivity by keeping a journal where I recorded my thoughts,

reactions, and positionality throughout the research. This transparent documentation enables others to trace how the interpretations emerged from the data, reinforcing the objectivity of the study. by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability Dependability refers to the stability and consistency of the research findings over time and under similar conditions. To achieve dependability, I systematically documented all steps of the research process, including the development of instruments, data-gathering techniques, and analytical strategies. I also sought peer debriefing from fellow researchers to review the process and ensure consistency in interpretations. Consequently, the study establishes a transparent and replicable process that future researchers can follow to verify or expand on the results. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the experiences of secondary school teachers in relation to their employment of inquiry-based learning to develop students' critical thinking skills, but it also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the research questions alongside the insights gathered from participants, offering a comprehensive view of the study's findings. The investigation focused on how inquiry-based learning cultivates critical thinking among students, as experienced by secondary school teachers. The study aimed to address three primary questions: the first explored the lived experiences of teachers in implementing inquiry-based learning; the second identified the strategies they employ to foster critical thinking; and the third examined the values and educational implications derived from the findings. Data analysis revealed several emerging themes. For the first question, themes such as shifting teacher roles, enhancing student engagement, and innovating pedagogies highlighted the transformative impact of inquiry-based approaches. In response to the second question, strategies such as scaffold instructional support, introduce intentional inquiry design and employ collaborative learning were identified as effective methods for developing critical

thinking. Lastly, the third question revealed values rooted in strengthening independent learning and engage in authentic inquiry

3.1. *Experiences in Cultivating Critical Thinking through Inquiry-Based Learning* —

Amid the growing demand for education that prepares students to think critically and solve complex problems, teaching practices are gradually shifting toward more student-centered approaches. Rather than relying solely on lectures or rote memorization, many educators are embracing methods that encourage curiosity, inquiry, and independent thought. This transition reflects a more profound commitment to

helping learners engage with content in ways that promote analysis, reasoning, and deeper comprehension. Teachers play a central role in this shift, drawing from their own classroom experiences to guide students through open-ended questions, collaborative investigations, and reflective discussions. Their journey in implementing these practices offers valuable perspectives on the realities of fostering critical thinking- shaped by both the opportunities and the constraints present in everyday teaching.

3.1.1. *Shifting Teacher Role*—A noticeable shift is underway in the classrooms of today, profoundly reshaping the educational experience for both teachers and students. Gone are the days when learning strictly adhered to a singular, teacher-centric model, where the educator stood as the unchallenged fount of all knowledge. Instead, it now presents a dynamic evolution and a redefinition of the teacher's purpose that moves beyond mere instruction. This transformation is particularly salient when considering how critical thinking is fostered through inquiry-based learning. In this evolving landscape, teachers are increasingly stepping into the role of facilitators, guiding students to become active participants in their discovery processes. This is not just a change in methodology; it is a fundamental reorientation toward empowering students to question, explore, and construct their understanding. The results of this study aligned with the findings of Ma (2021), particularly concerning the evolving role of teachers in inquiry-based learning. Ma emphasized that while inquiry-based learning enhances student engagement, it also presents the challenge of striking a balance between teacher guidance and student independence. Similarly, the participants in this study reported that their

roles shifted from traditional instructors to facilitators of learning. They encouraged students to ask questions, explore ideas, and collaborate in finding answers. This shift required them to adapt their teaching practices by developing stronger classroom management skills and demonstrating greater flexibility, confirming the dynamic and demanding nature of implementing inquiry-based instruction. This understanding of the teacher's role as a facilitator is further supported by Vongkulluksn et al. (2019), who observed increased student engagement in inquiry-based strategies due to heightened motivation and interest. By empowering students to explore topics stemming from their curiosities, teachers found that learners took greater ownership of their education. However, fostering this engagement required teachers to carefully plan activities that were both challenging and accessible, demonstrating their facilitative role in designing compelling learning experiences. The careful balancing act between providing structure and promoting independence is a hallmark of the facilitative approach. A salient strategy that embodies this facilitative role is guided inquiry, where teachers provide structured support to help students navigate complex topics while still fostering independent thought. Pedaste

(2020) highlighted that guided inquiry significantly enhances student learning outcomes by striking a balance between autonomy and support. In this approach, teachers actively scaffold learning, offering prompts, questions, or resources to steer students without providing direct answers. This method, particularly effective in science education, allows students to explore hypotheses with confidence, knowing they have a safety net provided by their facilitating teacher. He concluded that guided inquiry fosters more profound understanding and critical thinking precisely because it encourages students to take ownership of their learning, a direct result of the teacher's facilitative guidance. Similarly, Petersen (2022) found that guided inquiry effectively bridges the gap for students new to inquiry-based approaches, further solidifying the teacher's facilitative role. Teachers in this study emphasized the importance of pro-

viding structured, step-by-step guidance, particularly at the outset of the inquiry process. By utilizing questioning frameworks and pre-selected resources, teachers were able to guide students through complex subjects without overwhelming them. The study clearly showed that as teachers gradually reduced their level of support, students became more confident and developed independent inquiry skills more effectively. This gradual release of responsibility is a prime example of teachers embracing their role as facilitators, preparing students to lead their learning journeys eventually. By shifting the focus from direct instruction to guided and independent learning, educators empower students to take ownership of their growth. This approach fosters critical thinking and encourages active engagement, making learning more meaningful and student-centered.

3.1.2. Enhancing Student Engagement — Beyond the pedagogical shifts, a critical aspect of cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning lies in its profound impact on the learners themselves. When students are moved from passive recipients of information to active investigators, the very nature of their participation transforms. This engagement goes further than mere attendance; it signifies a deep, intrinsic involvement with the learning material, fueled by curiosity and the pursuit of answers. Moreover, this heightened level of interaction and enthusiasm is not an accidental byproduct; it is a direct consequence of learning environments that encourage questioning, exploration, and the active construction of knowledge. The participants have observed this transformation firsthand, noting how students become more invested when they are challenged to think critically and collaboratively. The responses of the participants corroborate with the convergence of studies, consistently highlighting the significant enhancement of student engagement

through inquiry-based learning. Vongkulluksn et al. (2019) reported a marked increase in student motivation and interest when inquiry-based strategies were employed. By allowing students to explore topics aligned with their curiosities, educators observed that learners assumed greater ownership of their educational journey. This heightened sense of ownership directly contributed to a more engaged and self-directed learning experience, ensuring that activities remained both challenging and accessible across diverse skill levels. This positive influence on engagement is further substantiated by Ma (2021), whose investigation confirmed that inquiry-based learning substantially elevates student engagement. While acknowledging the inherent challenge of navigating the balance between structured guidance and student autonomy, teachers in this study articulated a shift in their instructional role toward that of facilitators. This facilitative approach was observed to lead directly to augmented student involvement. Educators noted that while this

pedagogical shift fostered greater engagement, it concurrently necessitated enhanced classroom management skills and adaptability in teaching methodologies. Moreover, the integration of real-world problems into inquiry-based learning has been identified as a potent catalyst for student engagement. Lameris et al. (2021), examining the implementation of inquiry-based learning in science education in Finland, observed particularly elevated levels of student engagement when inquiry projects were directly connected to practical, everyday contexts. Teachers in this study consistently noted that when students perceived the immediate relevance of their learning to their own lives, their participation and enthusiasm demonstrably increased. These experiences underscore the critical importance of making learning contextual and personally meaningful, which significantly augments students' willingness to immerse themselves in the inquiry process, even as teachers navigate the complexities of aligning open-ended inquiry with established curriculum standards. The strategic incorporation of technology also plays a pivotal role in augmenting student engagement within inquiry-based frameworks. Al Mamun, Lawrie, and Wright (2020) explored

3.1.3. Innovating Pedagogies Adopting to Learners' Needs —Cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning in vibrant classrooms is a demanding yet rewarding endeavor that asks educators to be exceptionally versatile. This is not simply about employing a single teaching method but about the nuanced ability to adjust, modify, and innovate instructional strategies in real-time, responsive to the unfolding needs of student inquiry. It speaks to the teacher's skill in navigating unpredictable learning paths, providing tailored scaffolding, and recognizing opportune moments for deeper exploration, even when straying from a pre-planned lesson. This theme highlights the responsive and flexible expertise required to truly

the impact of digital tools in this context, with teachers emphasizing the benefits of resources such as online simulations and collaborative platforms. These technological aids not only intensified student engagement by enabling the real-time exchange of ideas and findings but also promoted inclusivity by accommodating diverse learning styles. This underscores how a well-supported integration of technology can cultivate a more dynamic and accessible inquiry environment, provided educators possess the requisite resources and training. On the other hand, compelling qualitative evidence consistently demonstrates that teachers perceive significant value in utilizing inquiry-based learning due to its profound impact on student engagement. Khalil and Gunduz (2023) reported that educators who have successfully implemented inquiry-based learning in their classrooms consistently observed greater student engagement alongside deeper cognitive processing and enhanced critical thinking abilities. These salient positive outcomes serve as a powerful motivator for teachers to persist with inquiry-based learning, even in the face of difficulties, affirming its long-term benefits for student learning and engagement as a valuable pedagogical approach.

empower students to question, investigate, and construct their knowledge, acknowledging that the journey of inquiry is rarely linear. The experiences of teachers, as described in various studies, strongly align with the challenges our participants encountered, particularly regarding the need for enhanced pedagogical adaptability in inquiry-based learning. Alvarez (2020) highlighted this directly, noting the difficulties teachers face when using open-ended questioning, especially in large or diverse classrooms. While open-ended questions are great for stimulating critical thinking, teachers reported they often demand more time and individual attention. In settings with limited resources or tight schedules, it became tough for educators to man-

age the wide range of student responses and ensure everyone had a chance to participate. This points to the need for teachers to be highly adaptable in their questioning and facilitation strategies. This need for adaptability extends to supporting diverse learners. Lorenz et al. (2021) examined how teachers can tailor open-ended questioning to serve multilingual classrooms better. Culturally responsive pedagogy plays a crucial role in making inquiry-based learning accessible to diverse learners. Teachers who recognize and value students' varied backgrounds can design inquiries that connect with learners' lived experiences, making the content more relevant and meaningful. Their research found that when teachers adjusted open-ended questions to match students' language abilities and cultural backgrounds, it significantly boosted engagement in the inquiry process. By allowing students to respond in multiple ways and fostering an environment where they could freely express their thoughts, this approach helped build confidence, especially for those who might struggle in traditional, lecture-based settings. This demonstrates how teachers must adapt their questioning techniques to be inclusive and effective for all learners. However, this increased need for adaptability is not without its challenges. Gholam (2019) noted that while guided inquiry strategies are effective for many, students with diverse learning needs or those from underprivileged backgrounds often require more specific support. Teachers in this study found it challenging to adjust the level of guidance for each student, particularly in large or mixed classrooms. This highlights a critical aspect of pedagogical adaptability: the ability to customize support levels on the fly to meet individual student needs, which often calls for ongoing professional development and resources. Furthermore, the very nature of collaborative learning in inquiry-based settings demands significant teacher adaptability. Thompson's (2018) study on collaborative inquiry projects showed that students developed improved analytical and critical thinking skills by engaging in peer discussions. During these interactions, students challenged each other's viewpoints and refined their arguments, which is vital for developing higher-order thinking. For teachers, facilitating this dynamic, collaborative process means adapting their role from direct instruction to guiding group interactions, mediating discussions, and fostering an environment where students feel comfortable exploring complex problems and diverse perspectives together. This continuous adjustment to student-led discovery is a hallmark of pedagogical adaptability in inquiry-based learning. Proficient inquiry-based facilitators are those who can adeptly balance structure and freedom, understanding when to intervene with probing questions and when to permit students to grapple with uncertainty. This transition in the role of instruction necessitates that educators possess robust observational and responsive teaching abilities, as they are required to continuously evaluate group dynamics, recognize misconceptions, and offer timely assistance without disrupting the flow of student inquiry. This adaptability not only enriches the depth of student engagement but also facilitates differentiated instruction that caters to learners at their respective levels. In conclusion, teacher adaptability is crucial not only for effective classroom management but also for fostering a learning environment where curiosity, critical reflection, and collaboration can flourish. Presented in figure 3 are the experiences of teachers in cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning. Three emerging themes were found namely: shifting teacher role, enhancing student engagement, and innovating pedagogies adopting to learners' needs.

3.2. *Coping Strategies on Cultivating Critical Thinking Through Inquiry-Based Learning* —

Fig. 3. Experiences on Cultivating Critical Thinking Through Inquiry-Based Learning.

Cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning is an enriching endeavor for educators, yet it presents its own unique set of complexities. As teachers empower students to explore questions and construct knowledge, they frequently encounter practical obstacles that demand ingenuity and perseverance. These challenges include navigating resource limitations, addressing student hesitancy to embrace inde-

pendent learning, or managing the dynamic and often unpredictable flow of an inquiry-driven classroom. Successfully fostering critical thinking in such an environment hinge on a teacher's ability to adapt and devise effective strategies to overcome these hurdles. It is in responding to these difficulties that educators truly hone their craft, ensuring that the transformative potential of inquiry-based learning is fully realized.

3.2.1. Scaffold Instructional Support— Guiding students to cultivate critical thinking through inquiry-based learning means embracing a dynamic and sometimes unpredictable classroom environment. There are moments when students, deeply immersed in their investigations, might hit a conceptual roadblock or feel uncertain about their next step. Rather than stepping in to provide direct answers, effective educators find ingenious ways to help students navigate these intellectual challenges on their own. This often involves a subtle yet powerful suite of supportive actions designed to empower learners to push past difficulties and uncover solutions independently. Such strategic interventions are not just teaching methods; they represent a fundamental coping mechanism for teachers themselves, enabling them to maintain the integrity of inquiry while ensuring students build resilience and deeper understanding. The participants' responses resonate strongly with broader pedagogical shifts, emphasizing the critical role of scaffolding support in inquiry-based learning. Guided inquiry, a widely adopted strategy, exemplifies this by having teachers provide structured guidance. As Pedaste (2020) highlighted, this approach significantly enhances student learning outcomes by balancing student autonomy with essential support, proving particularly effective in science education, where students confidently explore hypotheses knowing they have a supportive framework. This emphasis on scaffolding is crucial for introduc-

ing students to inquiry-based approaches. Petersen (2022) found that guided inquiry effectively bridges this gap, especially for newcomers. Teachers in this study highlighted the importance of providing structured, step-by-step guidance, particularly at the beginning of the inquiry process, and gradually reducing support as learners become more confident in developing independent inquiry skills. Beyond individual learning, scaffolding support also enhances collaborative efforts. Korkman (2021) observed the positive impact of guided inquiry on collaborative learning. Teachers in this study utilized guided inquiry strategies to encourage group work, where students shared responsibilities for researching and presenting their findings, fostering both content knowledge and essential teamwork and communication skills. Nevertheless, providing effective scaffolding can be complex, especially with diverse learners. Gholam (2019) noted challenges associated with guided inquiry, particularly in heterogeneous classrooms. Teachers reported that while guided inquiry worked well for many students, those with diverse learning needs or from underprivileged backgrounds often required additional, tailored support, highlighting the need for teachers to adapt the level of guidance based on individual student abilities. The effectiveness of scaffolding support in inquiry-based learning extends to specific educational contexts, such as the Philippines. Cruz and Villanueva (2021) explored its impact on Philippine high school

science education, finding that guided inquiry was highly effective in fostering scientific literacy and critical thinking by offering a valuable

balance between structure and independence, preparing students for future academic and professional endeavors.

3.2.2. Introduce Intentional Inquiry Design—As teachers pursue to nurture critical thinking, a shift from traditional methods is imperative- choosing to create learning environments where students actively question, explore, and make meaning from their experiences. This approach encourages learners to engage deeply with content and construct their understanding, which are key components in developing critical thought. Rather than simply delivering information, educators guide students through processes that require investigation, reflection, and reasoning. Hence, these practices foster intellectual curiosity and independence among learners. Participants' responses highlighted that strategic questioning is a vital element of effective inquiry design. Lozano (2021) supported this by emphasizing that open-ended questions guide students to engage more deeply with content and explore ideas beyond surface-level understanding. These types of questions encourage learners to reflect, ask follow-up questions, and consider multiple viewpoints. Such questioning techniques create a learning environment that supports critical exploration and intellectual growth, both of which are central to a strong inquiry framework. In shaping inquiry-based instruction, Zhang (2020) demonstrated that the thoughtful use of open-ended questions plays a key role in initiating and sustaining scientific inquiry. By asking questions that prompt prediction and investigation, teachers design opportunities for students to formulate hypotheses, test their ideas, and engage in reflective thinking. These practices help structure inquiry experiences that lead to improved problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding, showing how questioning can serve as an intentional de-

sign choice for promoting inquiry. Designing inquiry activities also involves recognizing and addressing classroom challenges. Alvarez (2020) pointed out that although open-ended questioning supports student thinking, its functional use demands time and careful facilitation. Teachers reported difficulty in managing diverse responses and ensuring balanced participation, especially in large or resource-limited classrooms. This finding underscores the need to design inquiry tasks that are both inclusive and manageable, suggesting the value of teacher training focused on structuring open-ended questioning in ways that support all learners. In designing inquiry tasks for social studies, Johnson (2020) highlighted how open-ended questions can be used to connect historical events to present-day issues. Questions that invite students to consider personal responses to past events or to relate those events to current challenges promote relevance and analytical depth. This study illustrates how inquiry design in the humanities can be enhanced by questions that lead students to draw meaningful connections and develop informed viewpoints. Moreover, Lorenz (2021) contributed insights into how inquiry design can support diverse and multilingual classrooms. The study found that when teachers adapted open-ended questions to align with students' language levels and cultural backgrounds, learners were more actively engaged. These adaptations allowed for varied forms of expression and encouraged collaborative exploration. The findings suggest that flexible, responsive inquiry design can create more inclusive learning environments, particularly when the questioning strategies are intentionally shaped to meet diverse student needs.

3.2.3. Employ Collaborative Learning—

In classrooms where inquiry thrives, learning is a shared journey rather than a solitary task. Teachers intentionally structure opportunities for students to engage with peers, exchange ideas, and challenge each other's thinking through dialogue and joint problem-solving. This interactive process deepens understanding and sharpens reasoning skills as learners negotiate meaning and refine their viewpoints in the presence of others. Through these collective engagements, students begin to recognize the value of multiple perspectives and the power of questioning in constructing knowledge. Participants' responses confirmed that collaboration plays a vital role in shaping inquiry-based learning experiences. Youngren (2021) supported this by showing that student engagement increases when inquiry tasks are completed collaboratively. The study found that working in groups encouraged learners to participate more actively, express their ideas freely, and take intellectual risks. Through group discussions and shared problem-solving, students experienced a more dynamic learning process, which contributed to deeper understanding and greater motivation. Furthermore, Thompson (2018) provided evidence that collaborative learning strengthens critical thinking in inquiry-based environments. The study revealed that students working together on inquiry tasks developed stronger analytical reasoning. During peer dis-

ussions, learners were encouraged to question assumptions, evaluate evidence, and refine their arguments. This interaction promoted intellectual rigor as students encountered different viewpoints and worked through problems using collective reasoning. In addition to cognitive benefits, collaborative learning also contributes to the development of classroom relationships and emotional support structures. Korkman (2021) found that students involved in collaborative inquiry felt a stronger sense of belonging and connection to their peers. The shared learning experience helped foster a positive and supportive learning environment. As students engaged in joint exploration, they built communication and teamwork skills while strengthening their social bonds within the academic setting. This sense of community not only enhances student motivation but also reduces anxiety and fear of failure, which are common barriers to participation in more traditional, teacher-centered classrooms. When students feel emotionally safe and supported by their peers, they are more likely to take intellectual risks, ask questions, and engage in deeper discussions. Presented in Figure 4, it encompasses the coping strategies of teachers in cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning. Three relevant themes emerged: scaffold instructional support, introduce intentional inquiry design, and employ collaborative learning.

3.3. Insights Drawn to Cultivate Critical Thinking Through Inquiry-Based Learning—Above merely acquiring skills and knowledge, the very act of engaging in deep inquiry shapes something more profound within learners. Teachers guide learners in rigorous questioning and evidence examination. Through this work, they cultivate vital intrinsic qualities.

These dispositions and principles emerge when learners navigate complex problems and seek truth. They extend beyond academic achievement; they foster intellectual and ethical character. This more profound impact is subtly yet powerfully woven into the fabric of inquiry-based learning. It manifests as principles guiding their approach to knowledge and interaction.

3.3.1. Strengthening Independent Learning—

Fig. 4. Coping Strategies on Cultivating Critical Thinking Through Inquiry-Based Learning

A remarkable transformation unfolds as students embrace their role as active participants. It is furthered as they are given the space and opportunity to question and explore their learning genuinely. As they delve into complex questions and construct their understanding, something fundamental shifts within them regarding their ownership of the learning process. It speaks to a growing sense of independence and responsibility for their educational journey, becoming critical thinkers because they inherently choose to be. This profound internal development, cultivated through inquiry, becomes a guiding principle in their approach to learning and problem-solving. The experiences of the participants resonate with broader pedagogical insights, underscoring how student autonomy is a crucial value in fostering critical thinking through inquiry-based learning. As Pedaste (2020) highlighted, guided inquiry significantly enhances student learning outcomes by striking a delicate balance between providing support and encouraging independent thought. This ap-

proach allows students to explore topics with a sense of freedom, prompting them to take ownership of their learning. It is in this space of self-directed exploration, where direct answers are withheld, and critical thinking is nurtured, that students truly develop more profound understanding and analytical skills. This emphasis on autonomy aligns with Ma's (2021) observations, which confirm that inquiry-based learning significantly boosts student engagement while simultaneously presenting the challenge of balancing guidance with student independence. Teachers in this study recognized the need to act as facilitators, shifting from traditional instruction to encouraging students to ask their questions and collaboratively seek answers. This shift, driven by a respect for student autonomy, ultimately led to greater engagement and demanded more flexible teaching approaches, demonstrating how valuing student freedom is integral to fostering critical thinking. For students new to inquiry-based approaches, cultivating autonomy begins with structured scaf-

folding. Petersen (2022) found that guided inquiry is particularly effective in bridging this gap. By providing structured, step-by-step guidance, especially at the outset, teachers enable students to explore complex subjects without feeling overwhelmed. As students gain confidence, teachers gradually reduce their level of support, allowing learners to develop independent inquiry skills more effectively. This systematic approach ensures that autonomy is built progressively, laying a strong foundation for critical thinking. The impact of valuing student autonomy extends even to specific educational contexts like the Philippines. Cruz and Villanueva (2021) found that guided inquiry was highly effective in fostering scientific literacy and critical thinking among high school science teachers. By providing research questions and structured tasks while simultaneously allowing room for student-driven exploration, teachers in the Philippines cultivated a balance between necessary guidance and the freedom for students to explore. This approach, rooted in student autonomy, helps to prepare learners for higher education and the workforce by developing essential inquiry skills. Moreover, the direct

benefits of fostering student autonomy are profound, particularly for their cognitive development and self-efficacy. Gu et al. (2015, as cited in Gholam, 2019) found that students involved in inquiry-based practices reported higher levels of academic self-efficacy, improved conflict resolution, and a greater willingness to take risks and persist through challenges. It highlights that when students are actively engaged in their inquiry, driven by their autonomy, they do not just master content; they cultivate essential habits of mind. Finally, the intentional use of open-ended questioning serves as a powerful tool for valuing and cultivating student autonomy in the development of critical thinking. Zhang and Patrick (2020) demonstrated this in science classrooms, observing that when teachers used open-ended questions, students were more likely to engage in crucial inquiry processes such as hypothesis generation, experimentation, and reflection. This approach directly encouraged students to formulate their investigations, leading to improved problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of scientific principles, all stemming from the freedom to think and explore independently.

3.3.2. Engage in Authentic Inquiry—The learning process unfolds most meaningfully when students begin to immerse themselves in purposeful exploration. As they navigate questions and pursue deeper understanding, their attention shifts from simply producing answers to examining how those answers are reached. The process invites close observation, thoughtful analysis, and a willingness to revise assumptions in light of new information. It becomes clear that insight does not emerge instantly but is shaped by careful reasoning and the steady refinement of ideas. Participants spoke of moments where their thinking evolved mid-way through a task, not because they were told what to think but because they discovered the value

of following a line of inquiry with curiosity and persistence. Their reflections point to a transformation, which emphasizes that learning becomes less about outcomes and more about the rigor and thoughtfulness brought to the journey. The participants' responses align with the evolving understanding that prioritizing process over content acquisition is crucial for cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning. Saavedra and Opfer (2020) strongly emphasize this, highlighting inquiry-based learning's critical role in fostering 21st-century skills like critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving. Their multi-country analysis revealed that inquiry-based learning deepens understanding by promoting active participation in learn-

ing processes, not just outcomes. This focus on the how of learning, on the journey of discovery, prepares students for modern complexities, making it a vital educational strategy globally. This emphasis on process is also central to the discourse on inquiry-based learning in Pakistan. Joseph, Sheikh, and Rajani (2022) underscore that teachers and educators are responsible for implementing inquiry-based learning to improve 21st-century skills such as creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication. They detail how traditional teaching methods often hinder genuine student learning precisely because they neglect the dynamic process of inquiry. By shifting focus to the investigative process, students are empowered to develop these crucial skills more effectively. Supporting this process-oriented approach, Vongkulluksn et al. (2019) reported increased student engagement when inquiry-based strategies were used, as students became more motivated and interested in the learning process itself. By allowing students to explore topics resonating with their curiosities, teachers observed learners taking greater ownership of their education. This ownership stems from valuing the investigative process, even though teachers noted that fostering this engagement required careful planning to ensure activities were both challenging and accessible. The importance of ongoing teacher professional development further highlights the value of focusing on the inquiry process. Gholam (2019) found that well-prepared teachers reported more positive experiences in fostering student engagement. These educators, equipped with training and support, felt more confident in guiding stu-

dents through the inquiry process effectively. This suggests that robust training is crucial for equipping teachers to manage the complexities of this process-driven approach and, in turn, enhance student engagement and critical thinking. Furthermore, the intentional use of open-ended questioning is another powerful tool for emphasizing the inquiry process in cultivating critical thinking. Zhang and Patrick (2020) found that when teachers used open-ended questions, students were more likely to engage in crucial inquiry processes such as hypothesis generation, experimentation, and reflection. This approach, by guiding students through the investigative steps rather than dictating solutions, directly led to improved problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of scientific principles. Finally, collaborative learning reinforces this process-oriented approach by encouraging students to engage deeply with content while developing critical interpersonal skills. Youngren (2021) observed that when students worked together on inquiry projects, their motivation and involvement in the learning process significantly increased. Collaborative tasks, such as group discussions and joint problem-solving, fostered a supportive environment where students felt comfortable expressing ideas and taking risks, ultimately contributing to a richer understanding as students learned from each other's insights throughout the investigative journey. Presented in Figure 5 are the values formulated in cultivating critical thinking through inquiry-based learning. The findings revealed two salient emerging themes: strengthening independent learning and engage in authentic inquiry.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter details the research questions and the insights gleaned from participants, providing a thorough overview of the study's findings. The investigation primarily aimed to explore how inquiry-based learning fosters critical thinking in secondary school students, as perceived by their teachers. The study addressed three core questions: the first examined teachers' experiences implementing inquiry-based learning; the second identified the strategies teachers use to cultivate

Fig. 5. Insights Drawn to Cultivate Critical Thinking Through Inquiry- Based- Learning

critical thinking; and the third explored the underlying values and educational implications drawn from the results. Data analysis revealed several significant themes.

4.1. Findings—In response to the first research question, three prominent themes emerged: shifting teacher roles, enhancing student engagement, and innovative pedagogies adopting to learners' needs. Participants frequently discussed how inquiry-based learning shifted their instructional roles from direct teaching to facilitating student discovery. This often led to increased student engagement, with learners becoming more invested in their educational journeys. However, this shift also demanded considerable innovative pedagogical adaptability as teachers continuously refined their strategies to suit the dynamic nature of inquiry-based methods. Moving to the second research question, which explored teachers' strategies for fostering critical thinking, three key themes surfaced: scaffold instructional support, introduce intentional inquiry design, and employ collaborative learning. Teachers highlighted the crucial role of scaffolding support, providing systematic assistance to help students navigate complex inquiries. Their narratives also underscored the importance of thoughtful inquiry design, as they consistently devised inventive ways to frame questions and activities that promoted deeper analysis. Furthermore, a commitment to collaborative exploration was evident, with teachers adjusting their methods to encourage active participation and critical thought among learners. Finally, the third research question, which investigated educational implications, revealed themes of strengthening independent learning and engage in authentic inquiry. The findings indicated substantial growth in student autonomy as students became more adept at directing their learning and problem-solving. Simultaneously, the study emphasized the potential for a greater focus on the learning process itself, demonstrating how inquiry-based approaches can prioritize the journey of discovery over rote memorization. These insights collectively suggest that effective inquiry-based learning is firmly supported by organized, collaborative efforts among educators and administrators- extending its benefits beyond immediate engagement to foster deeper understanding and improved critical thinking outcomes. Overall, this study offers a comprehensive examination of how secondary school teachers leverage inquiry-based learning to enhance critical thinking skills in students. It uncovers both the transformative impact on teaching practices and the adaptive strategies teachers employ to navigate these shifts. Ultimately, the findings provide crucial insights for educational management on how to effectively support the integration of student empowerment and a process-oriented approach, thereby creating a more stimulating and effective academic environment.

4.2. Implications—The study uncovered significant insights into how secondary school teachers implement inquiry-based learning, the instructional strategies they use to promote critical thinking, and the core values that guide their efforts to engage students in the learning process actively. Foremost, the theme of shifting teacher roles reveals a significant transformation in classroom dynamics. Rather than functioning solely as knowledge providers, teachers increasingly act as facilitators who guide students through the inquiry process. This shift suggests that educators could benefit from targeted professional development focused on inquiry-based learning techniques. Such training would support teachers in effectively encouraging student

exploration and independent thinking, thereby creating more engaging and dynamic learning environments. Moreover, enhancing student engagement emerged as a key outcome of inquiry-based learning. When students are actively involved in questioning, investigating, and collaborating, their motivation and participation increase substantially; therefore, educational programs and curricula should emphasize the design of learning experiences that foster curiosity and student involvement. By doing so, schools can promote deeper understanding and sustained interest in academic content. Additionally, innovative pedagogies adopting to learners' needs plays a crucial role in meeting the diverse needs of learners. The study indicates that teachers who adjust their instructional methods to suit different learning styles and contexts tend to support critical thinking more effectively. Consequently, educational leaders and policymakers may encourage flexible teaching approaches that empower educators to tailor their lessons while maintaining clear learning goals. Furthermore, scaffold instructional support was identified as an essential strategy for helping students navigate complex tasks. Providing appropriate guidance and resources enables learners to build confidence and develop higher-order thinking skills gradually. This finding points to the importance of instructional frameworks that balance challenge with support, ensuring students remain motivated without becoming overwhelmed. Another important strategy highlighted is introducing intentional inquiry design. Crafting well-structured inquiry tasks helps students engage meaningfully with content and develop their analytical abilities. Educational stakeholders should prioritize the development of curricula that incorporate thoughtful inquiry-based activities that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Employ collaborative learning also emerged as a valuable approach to fostering critical thinking. When students work together to investigate questions and share perspectives, they learn to evaluate different viewpoints and articulate reasoned arguments. This insight underscores the value of promoting cooperative learning environments where dialogue and interaction are central. Additionally, the value placed on strengthening independent learning reflects a broader educational shift toward learner-centered approaches. Encouraging students to take ownership of their learning processes supports the development of self-regulation and metacognitive skills. As a result, educators and curriculum designers should create opportunities for students to exercise independence while engaging deeply with the subject matter. Finally, the engagement in authentic inquiry highlights the importance of fostering reflective thinking. Prioritizing the learning journey rather than solely focusing on outcomes helps students develop critical thinking dispositions that extend beyond academic settings. This perspective encourages educational systems to cultivate environments where reflection and continuous improvement are integral to student growth. The findings of this study strongly align with Discovery Learning Theory, which asserts that learning occurs most effectively when students actively construct knowledge through exploration and discovery. The shifting teacher roles and enhanced student engagement reported by participants reflect the theory's emphasis on learner-centered approaches that foster autonomy and motivation. This demonstrates that inquiry-based learning supports the core principles of discovery learning by promoting active participation and self-guided inquiry. In the same vein, the study reinforces the Critical Thinking Framework by demonstrating how scaffolding, inquiry design, and collaborative learning facilitate higher-order thinking skills. These instructional strategies encourage students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information, core elements of critical thinking. The emphasis on student autonomy and process-oriented learning further validates the frame-

work's focus on reflective thinking and metacognition as integral to developing critical thinkers. In conclusion, this study highlights the transformative potential of inquiry-based learning to cultivate critical thinking in secondary education. The findings emphasize the importance of shifting teacher roles, enhancing student engagement, and adopting pedagogical adaptabil-

ity supported by effective scaffolding, inquiry design, and collaborative strategies. Grounded in Discovery Learning Theory and the Critical Thinking Framework, these insights provide a solid foundation for advancing inquiry-driven pedagogy that nurtures autonomous, reflective learners prepared to meet the demands of a complex world.

4.3. Future Directions—The insights gained from this study offer valuable guidance for stakeholders involved in advancing instructional practices in secondary education, particularly regarding the use of inquiry-based learning to enhance students' critical thinking skills. By highlighting teachers' experiences and strategies, the findings provide a foundation for developing more effective support systems and resources that promote active student engagement and deeper cognitive development.

Teachers

Secondary teachers can draw practical lessons from this study to refine their instructional approaches by integrating inquiry-based learning strategies that nurture critical thinking. Implementing scaffolding, designing purposeful inquiry tasks, and promoting collaborative exploration can increase student engagement and deepen understanding. Teachers are encouraged to adopt a flexible and reflective stance, adjusting their methods to students' readiness and interests while emphasizing the value of the learning process alongside academic outcomes. Learners The insights gained through this research can empower secondary learners to become active, self-directed learners. By engaging in inquiry activities that emphasize autonomy and collaborative problem-solving, students can strengthen their critical thinking and metacognitive skills. Understanding that educators aim to foster these competencies through inquiry-based learning may encourage learners to take ownership of their educational journey

and embrace opportunities for deeper intellectual engagement.

Parents

As education continues to embrace more meaningful and process-oriented approaches, parents are encouraged to become active partners in nurturing their children's capacity for exploration and curiosity. Future efforts may focus on equipping parents with strategies to support inquiry-based learning at home, such as encouraging thoughtful questioning, providing access to diverse resources, and allowing space for open-ended problem-solving. By fostering an environment where investigation and reflection are valued beyond the classroom, parents can play a pivotal role in sustaining their children's motivation to think critically, explore deeply, and learn independently. Continued collaboration between home and school will be essential in reinforcing the habits of mind that authentic inquiry seeks to develop.

School Administrators School heads and administrators may use these findings to guide strategic planning and policy development that fosters a school culture supportive of inquiry-based pedagogy. Emphasizing continuous professional growth through collaboration, resource accessibility, and instructional planning tailored to diverse learners can enhance teachers' ability to deliver inquiry-driven instruction. Providing structural support for these practices will better prepare educators to address the varied needs of students and promote critical thinking across different disciplines. Educational In-

stitutions responsible for pre-service teacher training and ongoing professional development can enrich their curricula by incorporating the study's insights on inquiry-based learning and critical thinking development. Emphasizing inquiry design, scaffolding techniques, and collaborative learning in training programs equips educators with the skills necessary to create engaging, adaptive, and reflective learning experiences. Developing mentorship opportunities, peer coaching, and hands-on practice can further prepare teachers to meet the challenges of diverse secondary classrooms and evolving educational demands. Department of Education (DepEd) This research provides valuable understanding for educational leaders in DepEd about the practical experiences teachers face when implementing inquiry-based learning. By recognizing how educators apply strategies such as scaffolding, inquiry design, and collaborative learning to foster critical thinking, leaders can support the creation of professional development programs that promote flexible, student-centered teaching approaches. Encouraging innovation and adaptability in instructional methods can help cultivate learning environments where critical thinking and active engagement are prioritized that contributes to an improved academic outcomes and lifelong learning skills.

Future Researchers This study lays a foundation for further investigation into the practices and outcomes of inquiry-based learning in secondary education. Future research could explore specific inquiry frameworks and strategies that best support critical thinking across various subject areas and learner profiles. Employing mixed methods such as classroom observations, teacher interviews, and student feedback would provide a richer understanding of how inquiry-based approaches function in real-world settings. Additionally, examining the influence of teacher beliefs, technological proficiency, and school context on the effectiveness of inquiry-based learning may offer new perspectives on instructional improvement. Ultimately, this study provides a compelling call to action for collaboration among educators, school leaders, teacher trainers, students, and researchers. Working together to refine and promote inquiry-based practices can lead to more engaging, meaningful, and critically enriching learning experiences, equipping secondary students with the skills needed to succeed in a complex and rapidly changing world.

5. References

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